

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This number contains only two papers. So: there is room for you in further editions, hurry up and submit some good stuff!

However, both papers in this issue are very special, both are co-authored by two of the most prominent persons who both worked at some time in Formal Language Theory and now are also leaving a deep impression in other more applied areas.

Karel Culik II, who became famous by solving the DOL equivalence problem; and the grand old man of formal language theory, Seymour Ginsburg, who influenced a generation of computer scientists.

By the way, if you want to read more about them, why don't you get hold of the very nice book *People and Ideas in Theoretical Computer Science*, C. Calude (Ed.), Springer Pub. Co., 1998, ISBN 981-4021-13-X ... and have a look e.g. at the paper "*Not only theory*"?

All the best,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
email: hmaurer@iicm.edu